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Identifying the Effective Factor of Knowledge Sharing System Acceptance from Knowledge Workers Perspective

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Abstract: Today we observe the rapid changes and intense complexity of environment. In such conditions, creating competitive advantages requires new kind of organizations that can create and manage knowledge. Sharing knowledge causes competitive advantages by reducing the costs and increasing the quality. Considering the fact that success in knowledge sharing systems depends on what is accepted and used by knowledge workers, it is important to identify the factors influencing knowledge sharing acceptance from knowledge workers perspective. Therefore, in this research, the effect of managerial, technical and human factors on knowledge sharing information systems acceptance has been assessed by a structural model. A questionnaire was prepared with 34 questions to conduct field studies on selected factors, which was confirmed by experts. Then it was distributed among knowledge workers to collect data in Tehran organizations that had implemented knowledge sharing system. The collected data was analyzed by correlation test, Freidman test and path analysis. The path analysis showed that effort expectancy, performance expectancy, senior management support, motivation, staff involvement, training and social influence have positive and direct effect on intension to use system and intension to use system also has direct and positive effect on real use of system. Facilitating condition has direct and positive effect on real use of the system. Friedman test indicated that the effective factors in order of priority and importance are: performance expectancy, effort expectancy, training, social influence, staff involvement, senior management support and motivation.

Keywords: Knowledge Sharing, Knowledge Sharing System, Affecting Factors on Knowledge Sharing System Acceptance, Knowledge Worker, Structural Equation Modeling.

